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Interaction dynamics between grouping principles in touch:
phenomenological and psychophysical evidence

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28

Abstract

29 In two experiments, we investigated the interactions between the grouping principles of
30 spatial-proximity and texture-similarity in touch. For that purpose, we adapted to touch
31 two paradigms widely employed in vision. In Experiment 1, we used an experimental
32 phenomenological task consisting of rating the strength of grouping in both acting-alone
33 and conjoined cooperative and competitive conditions. In Experiment 2, participants
34 performed a psychophysical task in which an objective (in)correct response was defined
35 by selectively attending to one grouping cue in different blocks of trials. The results
36 showed that spatial proximity dominated over texture similarity when the two principles
37 were conjoined in competition. In addition, the present results are compatible with an
38 additive model of grouping effects as indicated by the greater grouping effect in the
39 cooperative condition and the smaller grouping effect in the competitive condition
40 relative to acting-alone grouping principles. The similarities and differences between
41 vision and touch are discussed.

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44 **KEYWORDS:** cooperation; competition; perceptual grouping; spatial proximity;
45 texture-similarity; touch, haptic

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51 **1. Introduction**

52 Perceptual organization comprises a whole set of processes involved in how the
53 human brain organizes the incoming stream of perceptual information to build coherent
54 and relevant units that are the basis of integrated perception (Schmidt & Schmidt, 2013;
55 Wagemans, Elder, et al., 2012). An important organizational phenomenon is perceptual
56 grouping, which refers to the fact that observers perceive some elements of the scene as
57 going together more strongly than others (Wagemans, Elder, et al., 2012). The study of
58 perceptual grouping began with Wertheimer (1923) in the context of Gestalt
59 psychology. In his seminal work, he described and developed the main factors involved
60 in grouping the discrete elements of the perceptual scene.

61 During the second half of the 20th century, the topic of perceptual grouping was
62 examined from the perspective of experimental psychology, leading to the description
63 of a series of new grouping principles (Alais, Blake, & Lee, 1998; Palmer & Rock,
64 1994; Palmer, 1992; van den Berg, Kubovy, & Schirillo, 2011; Vickery, 2008), the
65 quantitative measurement of grouping, and the establishment of laws and models that
66 account for the grouping effects (Kubovy, Holcombe, & Wagemans, 1998; Kubovy &
67 Wagemans, 1995).

68 Even though the study of tactile perception has interested psychologists for a long
69 time, and that important perceptual issues have been addressed within this modality
70 from an experimental and neuroscientific approach (Ballesteros & Heller, 2008; Heller
71 & Ballesteros, 2006), the studies involving perceptual grouping and its functioning
72 mechanisms have focused almost exclusively on the visual and auditory modalities (see
73 Wagemans, Elder, et al., 2012; Wagemans, Feldman, et al., 2012, for an extensive
74 review). However, there has been recent renewed interest in the study of perceptual
75 grouping in the tactile modality (see Gallace & Spence, 2011, for a review of the history

76 of perceptual grouping in tactile perception), challenging former claims about the lack
77 of applicability of the grouping principles to touch (Révész, 1953), the difficulties
78 related to its serial nature (Grunwald, 2008; Lederman & Klatzky, 2009), and drawing
79 on the fact that some features such as surface texture and hardness are more salient for
80 touch than for vision (Klatzky, Lederman, & Reed, 1987). Specifically, Chang, Nesbitt,
81 and Wilkins (2007a, 2007b) found that participants grouped visual and tactile patterns
82 in a similar way using different grouping principles. More recently, Overvliet, Krampe,
83 and Wagemans (2012, 2013) found that proximity and similarity cues influenced
84 contour detection and haptic search, respectively. Moreover, proximity grouping and
85 certain configural cues speeded up the haptic search (Verlaers, Wagemans, & Overvliet,
86 2015; Overvliet & Plaisier, 2016). This body of work demonstrates that some grouping
87 principles operate in the tactile modality and influence other cognitive processes, and
88 that the laws that govern the processes of perceptual grouping in haptic and
89 visual/auditory modalities could be comparable to some extent. This is consistent with
90 previous research in touch, which found shared mechanisms between sensory modalities
91 in a number of perceptual phenomena such as symmetry detection, perceptual illusions
92 and repetition priming (Ballesteros & Reales, 2004; Ballesteros & Reales, 2005; Heller
93 & Joyner, 1993).

94 The quantitative study of the interactions that occur when different grouping
95 principles act conjointly have received considerable attention in vision. That is, when
96 the combined principles act in *cooperation* (i.e., when the grouping principles are
97 conjoined in such a way that they strengthen a certain stimulus configuration) or in
98 *competition* (i.e., when the grouping principles operate against each other, strengthening
99 different stimulus configurations and producing ambiguous and unstable perceptual

100 organizations) (Kubovy & van den Berg, 2008; Luna, Villalba-García, Montoro, &
101 Hinojosa, 2016; Quinlan & Wilton, 1998; Schmidt & Schmidt, 2013).

102 This line of research has pursued two main objectives. The first was to find a model
103 accounting for the observed separate and combined effects of the grouping principles.
104 Specifically, Kubovy and van den Berg (2008) proposed an additive model of the
105 grouping effects, which predictions can be tested under experimental conditions.
106 According to their model, additive effects can be inferred if: (1) the grouping strength of
107 the cooperation condition is greater than the grouping strength of either principle acting
108 alone; and (2) the grouping strength when the two principles are combined in
109 competition is weaker than either principle acting alone. The second objective was to
110 identify the rules that determine which principles dominate the perceived organization
111 when two grouping cues are combined (Han & Humphreys, 1999; Palmer & Beck,
112 2007; Schmidt & Schmidt, 2013). In this case, the classic rules of processing dominance
113 are assumed (Navon, 1977, 1981; Pomerantz, 1983; Ward, 1983). Thus, a grouping cue
114 will dominate the perceived organization if: 1) it produces faster and/or more accurate
115 responses; 2) there is less interference from the competitive presence of the other cue; 3)
116 it leads to greater improvement of the responses to the other cue when it is presented in
117 cooperation; and/or 4) it is perceived under shorter exposure times.

118 Two main types of paradigm have been employed to achieve these goals. The first
119 is the “experimental phenomenological method” (Kubovy & Gephstein, 2003) in which
120 participants are asked to directly report spontaneous grouping without any specific
121 instruction about what should be perceived. The second paradigm uses psychophysical
122 tasks (Kubovy & Gepshtein, 2003; Palmer, 2003). This requires the inclusion of an
123 objective correct response by transforming the perceptual experience, either by forcing
124 observers to judge certain aspects of the stimulus or by hindering their perception. In

125 this case, perceivers engage mechanisms not involved in the natural perception of the
126 scene. This method makes it possible to analyze performance in terms of accuracy
127 and/or response times, at the cost of provide only indirect measures of grouping.

128 Given the lack of research addressing the laws that govern the interactions between
129 the grouping principles in touch, the present study aimed to investigate quantitatively
130 how different grouping cues interact during the process of perceptual organization to
131 generate an organized tactile percept. The main objectives of the present study were: 1)
132 to investigate the compatibility of the haptic data with an additive model of the effects
133 of grouping principles; and 2) to examine the dominance dynamics of both single and
134 conjoined grouping principles. This approach will allow us to test the facilitation effect
135 of cooperative cues, the interference/inhibitory effects of competing cues, and whether
136 performance in conjoined conditions could be predicted from performance in single
137 condition.

138 To achieve these objectives, we conducted 2 experiments in which we confronted
139 two well-known grouping principles: spatial proximity and texture similarity (Prieto,
140 Mayas, & Ballesteros, 2014) . In Experiment 1 we employed a phenomenological
141 method consisting of a rating task to estimate the strength of grouping in single (acting
142 alone) and conjoined (cooperative and competitive) conditions. The task was similar to
143 one used previously in vision (Quinlan & Wilton, 1998). We expected that grouping
144 would be strengthened when the two principles cooperate, leading to a more stable
145 organization and higher ratings relative to single grouping principles acting alone. By
146 contrast, grouping would weaken when the two principles compete, resulting in an
147 unstable percept. This would lead to lower scores on the rating scale. We also expected
148 that the dominance of one grouping principle in the competition condition would be
149 determined by the relative strength of the principles acting alone. If different relative

150 strengths occurred, the strongest principle would win the competition. No dominance
151 should be observed if the relative strengths were similar.

152 In Experiment 2, we employed a psychophysical method derived from one
153 previously used in vision (Luna et al., 2016), in which a correct response was
154 objectively defined. We hypothesized that if a grouping cue produces faster and more
155 accurate responses, if there is less interference from a second competitive cue, or if it
156 leads to greater facilitation when it is presented as a cooperative non-attended cue, it
157 could be concluded that the grouping cue dominates the haptic perceptual grouping
158 process. We also expected that the dominance dynamics would be congruent with the
159 results of Experiment 1. If one grouping cue showed greater relative strength or
160 dominated the ratings in the competitive condition in Experiment 1, then that grouping
161 cue would dominate the grouping process in Experiment 2.

162 **2. Experiment 1. Perceived phenomenological strength**

163 In this experiment, we tested the phenomenological strength of perceptual
164 organization when the grouping principles act alone or interact in a cooperative or
165 competitive manner.

166 The experimental procedure consisted of a rating task in which participants were
167 asked to rate the degree to which the central target grouped with either the left or right
168 cohort of flankers, using a 9-point scale. We followed the simple assumption that the
169 participants' estimates of the strength of grouping reflect the interactions (cooperation
170 and competition) between the grouping cues directly.

171 **Methods**

172 *2.1.1. Participants*

173 Twenty students (3 males; age range: 19-48, mean age = 28.53, SD = 8.64) at the
174 Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED) participated in Experiment 1

175 as part of a second-year course. Eighteen were right-handed and all had normal tactile
176 perception and were naïve to the purpose of the experiment. Before the experiment
177 started, participants completed a Spanish adaptation of the Edinburgh Handedness
178 Inventory (Bryden, 1977; Oldfield, 1971) and signed an informed consent for
179 participation in the study. The experimental protocol was approved by the Ethics
180 Committee of the Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia and was in
181 accordance with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki (Williams, 2008;
182 WMA General Assembly, 1964).

183 2.1.2. Apparatus

184 We used a device specifically designed for haptic exploration (Haptic
185 Monitor/MonHap) inspired by an apparatus used with monkeys (Fagot, Arnaud,
186 Chlambretto, & Fayolle, 1992). It consisted of an opaque box with two platforms
187 containing an array of 10 x 10 sockets in which the tactile stimuli can be plugged to
188 create the desired configuration. It has two openings for the hands, allowing for single-
189 and two-handed exploration of the tactile displays. The MonHap was interfaced with a
190 computer to control for stimulus presentation, and to record the responses and
191 exploration times (se Figure 1 left).

192 2.1.3. Stimuli

193 Each haptic display consisted of 6 touch-sensitive cylinders and 1 touch-sensitive
194 cube that were specifically designed for the MonHap device (Figure 1 right shows the
195 individual stimuli). The top of the cylinders was circular (13mm in height x 15mm in
196 diameter), while the top of the cube was square (13mm in height x 15mm in width). As
197 the participants only explored the top surface of the cylinders/cube, from now on we
198 will refer to them as circles/squares. Some individual stimuli were covered with
199 sandpaper to create a rough texture, while others retained their original smooth metallic

200 texture. In each trial, the circles/squares were arranged in a single row of seven
201 elements. The central stimulus (the target) was always a square. The other six elements
202 were circular and were organized in two cohorts (right and left, made up of three
203 elements each) that flanked the target.

204 **Fig. 1** a): a view of the Haptic monitor. b): schematic representation of the touch-
205 sensitive individual elements used in the haptic displays

206

207 A total of 18 different haptic displays were designed for the five different
208 conditions shown in Figure 2. In the no-grouping displays (baseline), it was not possible
209 to group the central target with the elements of the right or left cohort by means of any
210 grouping principle. In the displays for grouping principles acting alone, the target could
211 be grouped with the elements of the right (rightward display) or left (leftward display)
212 cohort, by means of only one of the two grouping principles (proximity or texture
213 similarity). In the two remaining conjoined conditions, the two principles were
214 combined. In the conjoined cooperative displays, the two principles acted together so
215 that the target could be grouped with the elements of either the right or the left cohort.
216 In the conjoined competing displays, each principle competed to group the target with
217 the elements of the right and left cohort, respectively. In the displays containing
218 different proximity conditions, the distance between spatially close elements was 6 mm,
219 while the distance between the spatially distant elements was 24 mm. In the displays
220 containing only different texture similarity conditions, the distance between the
221 elements was set at 6 mm.

222 **Fig. 2** Representation of displays for all the conditions in Experiment 1: (1) no
223 grouping; (2) proximity only; (3) texture similarity only; (4) cooperation between
224 grouping principles, and (5) competition between grouping principles

225

226 2.1.4. Design and procedure

227 A single-factor repeated measures design was used, including the within-subjects
228 factor *grouping condition* with four different conditions: proximity and similarity acting
229 alone, and combinations of these two grouping principles, either in cooperation or in
230 competition.

231 At the beginning of the experimental session participants received verbal
232 instructions. They also received comprehensive written instructions on the computer
233 screen before the experiment started.

234 Participants were tested individually in a quiet and dimly lit room of our laboratory.
235 The task consisted of rating the degree to which the target (the central square element)
236 could be grouped with either the left or the right cohort of elements using a 9-point
237 scale. Participants indicated verbally a number between 1 and 9. They were informed
238 that a value of 5 represented the feeling that the target did not group with either the left
239 or the right cohort. Ratings below 5 indicated that the target tended to group with the
240 right (counterbalance 1) or the left (counterbalance 2) cohort of elements. Ratings above
241 5 indicated that the target tended to group with the left (counterbalance 1) or the right
242 (counterbalance 2) cohort of elements. Participants were asked to consider the
243 numerical distance from the central point of the scale as being directly proportional to
244 the perceived grouping strength.

245 During the experimental session, participants were comfortably seated in front of
246 the haptic device with their dominant hand introduced through one of the two apertures
247 of the apparatus to explore the haptic stimuli. As participants could not see inside the
248 device, the experimenter guided their hands to the start position before the beginning of
249 each trial (the edge of the right hand placed near the stimulus without touching it). A
250 green led light placed in front of the participant's eyes signaled the start of the trial.

251 Participants were instructed to place their index and middle fingers at the beginning of

252 the row, exploring the pattern sequentially without stopping or going back, and give a
253 verbal rating. The beginning of the trial was determined automatically by the first
254 contact of the participant's hand with the stimulus. The cylinders were touch sensitive
255 and sent a signal to the computer immediately after the first contact with the stimulus.
256 At the end of the trial, the next random-generated stimulus was displayed on the
257 computer screen. The experimenter registered the participant's answer on the response
258 sheet and configured the next haptic display by plugging the stimuli on the presentation
259 platform. The participants then started the new trial. This procedure was repeated until
260 the 90 experimental trials were completed (10 baseline trials plus 20 trials in each of the
261 four grouping conditions). In addition to the counterbalanced rating scale, half of the
262 participants in each counterbalanced group explored the haptic stimulus starting from
263 the left side of the haptic display (left to right exploration), while the other half started
264 the exploration from the right (right to left exploration). Participants completed 4 to 8
265 practice trials before the start of the experimental session until they understood the
266 experimental procedure. The whole experimental session lasted about 45 minutes.

267 2.2. Results

268 The data from one participant was not entered into the data analysis due to lack of
269 understanding of the instructions. Prior to the statistical analyses, the raw scores were
270 transformed following the procedure described by Quinlan and Wilton (1998). We
271 collapsed the data from rightward and leftward displays and from the different rating-
272 scale counterbalances to compute a measure reflecting the perceived strength of
273 grouping in the direction of the designated dominant cohort. For example, 4 and 6
274 indicate the same strength of grouping in the two cases, even though each response
275 reflects grouping in different absolute directions, depending on the type of display
276 (rightward or leftward) and the specific scale counterbalance (1-9; 9-1). Therefore, in

277 the displays for grouping principle acting alone, the dominant cohort was defined by the
278 grouping principle itself (same texture as the target in similarity displays and nearest to
279 the target in proximity displays). In the conjoined cooperating displays, the dominant
280 cohort was defined by the conjoined effect of the two principles. In the conjoined
281 competing displays, the dominant cohort was established arbitrarily to the nearest
282 cohort (proximity). Finally, in the no-grouping displays, the dominant cohort was
283 established as the left cohort. Accordingly, individual rating scores were transformed to
284 a scale ranging from -4 to +4, where the negative 4 reflects maximal grouping in the
285 direction opposite to the dominant cohort, 0 reflects the absence of grouping in any
286 direction and the positive 4 indicates maximal grouping in the direction of the dominant
287 cohort.

288 2.2.1. Data for no-grouping condition (baseline)

289 First, we examined the data from the no-grouping condition to identify possible
290 systematic response biases. Zero indicates absence of bias, whereas positive and
291 negative scores indicate a bias toward the dominant and non-dominant cohort,
292 respectively. Table 1 shows the transformed scores for each condition. The mean rating
293 of the no-grouping condition was tested against a predicted value of 0 using one sample
294 *t*-test. No systematic bias was found in the ratings [$t_{18} = 1.80$; $p = .09$; $d = .41$]. The
295 inspection of the mean individual ratings showed that 16 out of 19 participants rated the
296 no-grouping condition as 0, and the other 3 rated the no-grouping condition as 0.20,
297 0.30 and 0.20, respectively. These results suggest that there was no systematic bias. The
298 data corresponding to the no-grouping displays were excluded from the remaining
299 analyses.

300

301 **Table 1** Summary of statistics for the different grouping conditions

Condition	Transformed mean rating	Standard deviation
No grouping (baseline)	.04	.10
Proximity	2.38	.80
Similarity	2.25	.80
Proximity ○ Similarity	3.40	.48
Proximity ÷ Similarity	.76	1.26

302 ○, cooperation; ÷, competition

303 2.2.2. Data corresponding to the four grouping conditions

304 Figure 3 (left) represents the transformed ratings for the 4 remaining grouping
 305 conditions. We first tested the presence of any grouping effects by comparing the
 306 observed mean rating of each grouping condition with an expected value of 0 by using
 307 the one sample t-test. The effect of grouping was significant in all conditions: proximity
 308 only [$t_{18} = 12.98$; $p < .001$; $d = 2.98$], similarity only [$t_{18} = 12.24$; $p < .001$; $d = 2.81$],
 309 cooperation [$t_{18} = 30.97$; $p < .001$; $d = 7.11$] and competition [$t_{18} = 2.62$; $p = .017$; $d =$
 310 $.60$].

311 **Fig. 3** a): transformed ratings for each grouping condition (the bars represent ± 1 SE). b):
 312 normalized effect sizes used to examine the compatibility of the present data with
 313 additive effects of grouping principles (Kubovy & van den Berg, 2008). Cooperation
 314 between principles is identified by (○) and competition by (÷)

315 Next, to determine whether the grouping strength varied across the four conditions
 316 that showed significant grouping effects in the previous analysis, the transformed
 317 ratings were entered in a one-way repeated measure ANOVA with grouping condition
 318 as a fixed factor and participants as a random factor. The analysis showed a main effect
 319 of grouping condition [$F_{3, 16} = 29.76$; $p < .001$; $\eta^2 p = .623$]. To compare the grouping
 320 effect size corresponding to the different conditions, the main effect was analyzed
 321 further using Bonferroni corrected post-hoc comparisons. These comparisons revealed
 322 that the two conditions with grouping principles acting alone produced similar grouping
 323 effects ($p > 0.05$). Conjoined cooperating principles produced greater grouping effects
 324 than acting-alone conditions (all $ps < .001$) and conjoined competing principles ($p <$

325 .001). Finally, the competing principles condition had lower grouping effects than
326 proximity ($p < .001$) and similarity ($p = .016$) acting alone and the conjoined
327 cooperating principles condition ($p < .001$).

328 In sum, the data reveal that the greatest grouping effect occurred when the two
329 grouping principles cooperated. When the two grouping principles acted alone, a
330 significant and reliable grouping effect appeared, which was similar for the two
331 grouping principles. Lastly, a small but significant grouping effect in the proximity
332 direction was found when the two principles were pitted against each other. The
333 general pattern of results obtained in touch indicates the existence of independent
334 effects of grouping by proximity and grouping by similarity, as well as a combined
335 effect of the conjoined principles that was slightly weaker than the sum of their separate
336 effects and a little stronger than the difference between them.

337 Finally, an interesting finding was that the error bars in the competition conditions
338 were larger than in the other conditions. A visual inspection of the individual ratings
339 showed that while some participants tended to group by proximity ($n = 14$), others
340 tended to group by similarity ($n = 5$). Thus, rather than cancelling each other out, the
341 participants showed a preference for proximity or similarity grouping in their ratings,
342 which is congruent with the greater variability seen in the competition condition.

343 2.2.3. Individual consistency

344 To further analyze the difference in score variability, we conducted an analysis of
345 the participants' individual ratings, to provide additional information about the
346 consistency of the scores in the different grouping conditions. To this end, we followed
347 the strategy used in vision (Luna & Montoro, 2011). First, we conducted homogeneity
348 of variance tests (HOV) to compare the variances of scores in all conditions, using t -
349 tests for the difference of variances in correlated samples (Zhang, 1998).

350
$$t = \frac{S_1^2 - S_2^2}{[(1 - r^2)4S_1^2S_2^2 / (n - 2)]^{0.5}}$$

351 where S_1^2 = variance under one condition
 352 S_2^2 = variance under the other condition
 353 r = correlation between conditions 1 and 2
 354 n = sample size

355 The results showed that the variance in the competition condition was significantly
 356 higher than in the other grouping conditions (one-tailed t-tests, all $ps < 0.05$), while the
 357 variance in the cooperation condition was significantly lower than in all the other
 358 grouping conditions. Finally, no difference was observed in the variance in the acting-
 359 alone principle conditions ($ps > 0.05$). These results might reflect: 1) a lack of
 360 consistency in responses to the competitive displays, leading to inconsistent ratings not
 361 related to the individual strength of each grouping principle in the acting-alone
 362 conditions; or 2) greater inter-individual variability, resulting in some participants
 363 consistently grouping by proximity, and others consistently grouping by similarity.

364 We performed an additional analysis to test whether participants showed the same
 365 pattern of integration results for cooperation and competition conditions. Thus, we
 366 analyzed whether the participants who demonstrated a stronger proximity grouping
 367 effect in the acting-alone conditions also showed positive ratings in the competition
 368 condition, and whether the participants who demonstrated a greater grouping effect for
 369 the similarity grouping in the acting-alone conditions showed negative ratings in the
 370 competition condition. In the cooperative displays, we tested whether the participants
 371 whose grouping scores were higher in the acting-alone conditions also had higher
 372 ratings in the cooperation condition. Next, we computed for all participants the bivariate
 373 correlation between the sum of scores in each acting-alone principle and the score in the
 374 cooperation condition; and the bivariate correlation between the difference in scores for

375 each acting-alone principle and the score in the competition condition. A moderate
376 significant correlation was found between the sum of the effects in acting-alone
377 conditions and the grouping ratings in the cooperation condition ($r = +.444, p = 0.03$).
378 Interestingly, a significant strong correlation was found between the difference in the
379 acting-alone grouping effects and the competition condition ($r = +.745, p < .001$). These
380 findings indicate that participants were generally consistent in their ratings, especially in
381 the competition condition even though the score variability was higher. The participants
382 who rated the grouping effects of proximity higher than similarity tended to have
383 positive scores in the competition condition. On the other hand, participants who rated
384 proximity lower than similarity tended to have negative scores in the competition
385 condition. Thus, the increased variability in the competition condition does not seem to
386 be attributable to the inconsistency of the competition condition ratings.

387 2.2.4. Compatibility with an additive model of grouping effects

388 To analyze the compatibility of the present data with the additivity of grouping
389 effects, we followed the procedure used by Kubovy and van den Berg (2008) in their
390 reinterpretation of the data from Quinlan and Wilton (1998). These authors pointed out
391 that the key to infer the additivity of grouping principles in this kind of experiment
392 relies on the effect found in the two conjoined conditions. First, to be compatible with
393 an additive model, the grouping effect of the two principles conjoined in cooperation
394 must be greater than either of the two principles acting alone. Second, the grouping
395 strength when the two principles are conjoined in competition should be smaller than
396 the grouping effect of either grouping principle acting alone.

397 We normalized the data by using the effect size D instead of the mean transformed
398 rating R ($D = R/\text{Standard error of } R$). Next, we adjusted the D values to fall between 0
399 and 1, by assuming the highest D value obtained as the 1 in the normalized scale and

400 computing the rest of the normalized effect sizes as the ratio between the observed D
 401 value and the highest D value ($D / \text{highest } D \text{ value observed}$) (Kubovy & van den Berg,
 402 2008). The normalized results are shown in Figure 3-right and the inferences about
 403 additivity are listed in Table 2.

404 **Table 2** Experiment 1. Inferences about the compatibility of the data with additivity of
 405 grouping

Data	Inference	Relation to additivity		
		Compatible	Not incompatible	Incompatible
$D(p \circ s) > D(p)$	The \circ combination of p and s is stronger than p	✓		
$D(p \circ s) > D(s)$	The \circ combination of p and s is stronger than s	✓		
$D(p \div s) < D(p)$	The \div combination of p and s is not stronger than p	✓		
$D(p \div s) < D(s)$	The \div combination of p and s is not stronger than s	✓		
$D(p \circ s) > D(p \div s)$	The \circ combination of p and s is stronger than the \div combination of p and s	✓		
$D(p \circ s) > D(p) > D(s)$ $> D(p \div s)$	The \circ combination of p and s is stronger than p , s and the \div combination of p and s	✓		

406 D represents the normalized measure of effect sizes; p , proximity; s , similarity; \circ ,
 407 cooperation; \div , competition

408 The results show that the normalized effect sizes of each principle acting alone
 409 were very similar and fell between the two conjoined conditions. When proximity and
 410 similarity cooperated, the grouping effect was greater than that of each acting-alone
 411 principle. On the other hand, when the two principles competed, the grouping effect was
 412 lower than either grouping principle acting alone.

413

414

415 **3. Experiment 2**

416 Experiment 1 showed that when the proximity and similarity grouping principles
417 were conjoined in competition in a task in which participants were asked to directly
418 report spontaneous grouping without specific instructions on what should be perceived,
419 proximity dominated the resulting organization even when the two principles were
420 equated in perceived grouping strength. Experiment 2 further explored which principle
421 dominated the perceived organization when two grouping cues were conjoined in
422 cooperation and competition. To this end, we examined the dominance dynamics of
423 conjoined grouping cues, using a grouping paradigm in which participants had to
424 discriminate the orientation (right or left) of groups based on two different cues
425 presented in different blocks, similar to the one used in the visual modality (Luna et al.,
426 2016). This paradigm introduces objectively correct responses by forcing the
427 participants to perceive the grouped displays in a specific way (Han, 2004; Han, Ding,
428 & Song, 2002; Palmer & Nelson, 2000).

429 We will focus on dependent measures of perceptual dominance used in previous
430 visual studies (Navon, 1977, 1981; Pomerantz, 1983; Ward, 1983). Thus, a grouping
431 cue will dominate processing if: 1) it leads to faster or more accurate responses; 2) there
432 is less interference from the competitive presence of the other cue; and 3) it facilitates
433 the response to the other cue when it is presented in cooperation with it.

434 *3.1. Method*

435 *3.1.1. Participants*

436 A new group of 20 students (5 males; age range: 20-45, mean age = 29.79, SD =
437 7.68) from the Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED) participated in
438 this Experiment. The participants reported normal tactile perception and were naïve to
439 the purpose of the experiment. As in Experiment 1, before the experiment started

440 participants completed a Spanish adaptation of the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory
441 (Bryden, 1977; Oldfield, 1971) and signed an informed consent form. The experimental
442 protocol was approved by the local Ethics Committee and is in accordance with the
443 ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki (Williams, 2008; WMA General
444 Assembly, 1964).

445 3.1.2. Apparatus and stimuli

446 The apparatus and stimuli were the same as those used in Experiment 1, except that
447 the no-grouping condition was not included. Thus, a total of 16 stimuli were used in
448 three experimental conditions: 1) acting-alone displays (single); 2) cooperative displays;
449 and 3) competitive displays. Textures and distances between elements were the same as
450 in Experiment 1 to ensure equivalent grouping strength of each cue.

451 3.1.3. Design and procedure

452 The 3 x 2 repeated measures design included two within-subject factors, *grouping*
453 *condition* (single, cooperative, competitive) and *directed attention* (attention directed to
454 groups based on proximity or texture similarity).

455 The experimental session lasted about 50 minutes, divided into two blocks of 20-25
456 minutes with a resting interval between them. The task consisted of discriminating the
457 orientation (right or left) of groups based on different grouping cues (proximity and
458 similarity) selectively attended to in different blocks of trials, while the other grouping
459 cue was ignored. For example, in the proximity block, participants had to attend and
460 respond only to the groups based on spatial proximity, while ignoring those based on
461 texture similarity. By contrast, in the similarity block, participants attended and
462 responded to groups based on texture similarity and ignored those based on spatial
463 proximity.

464 The exploration instructions were the same as in Experiment 1, except that
465 participants now used the index fingers of both hands to explore the stimuli. At the
466 beginning of each trial, participants placed their index fingers on either side of the
467 tactile display in contact with the side of the cylinders without touching their surfaces.
468 Next, they explored the surface of the patterns sequentially with both index fingers
469 without stopping or going back, until the two index fingers touched, approximately in
470 the center of the stimulus. Participants responded using the foot pedals located under
471 their right (for right responses) and left (for left responses) feet. Participants were also
472 asked to explore and respond as fast and accurately as possible, and to move their index
473 fingers at the same time and the same speed.

474 RTs and accuracy were recorded as dependent variables. The number of
475 experimental trials was 112, divided into two blocks of 56 trials with a rest interval
476 between them. Participants completed 4 practice trials at the beginning of each block to
477 ensure that they understood the experimental procedure. The order of the proximity and
478 similarity blocks was counterbalanced across participants.

479 3.2. Results

480 3.2.1. Response time and error rates

481 The data from one participant were not included in the analysis because he reported
482 a motor pathology that could interfere with speeded responses. Therefore, all the
483 analyses were conducted on the remaining 19 subjects. Response times (RTs) to
484 incorrect responses and those above or below 3 standard deviations from the mean were
485 removed from the analysis. The remaining RTs and the error rates were analyzed in two
486 separate repeated measures ANOVAs, with 2 x *directed attention* (proximity or texture
487 similarity) and 3 x *grouping condition* (single, cooperative and competitive) within-

488 subjects factors. The relevant data are summarized in Figure 4 and Table 3. All the
 489 analyses were Bonferroni corrected.

490 **Fig. 4** Mean response times in ms (a) and error rates in % (b) for directed attention and
 491 grouping conditions. The error bars represent ± 1 SE

492

493 **Table 3** Mean response time (ms) and standard deviations (in brackets) for each
 494 condition in Experiment 2

Directed attention					
	Single	Coop.	Fac.	Comp.	Interf.
Proximity	1606 (307)	1602 (293)	-4 (103)	1683 (318)	77 (143)
Similarity	2059 (491)	2030 (429)	-29 (184)	2212 (530)	153 (147)
Advantage	453	428		529	

495 Fac.: cooperative RTs – single RTs; Interf.: competitive RTs – single RTs

496 The analysis of the RT data showed a main effect of *directed attention* [$F_{1, 18} =$
 497 $36.15; p < .001; \eta^2 p = .668$], indicating shorter RTs for proximity groupings (1630 ms)
 498 than for texture similarity groupings (2100 ms). The main effect of *grouping condition*
 499 also reached statistical significance [$F_{2, 17} = 36.15; p < .001; \eta^2 p = .668$]. Pairwise
 500 comparisons indicated that responses in single and cooperative conditions were faster
 501 than responses in the competitive condition ($p = .004$ and $p < .001$ respectively). No
 502 other effects reached statistical significance.

503 The ANOVA conducted on error rates showed no significant main effects, but the
 504 interaction between *directed attention* and *grouping condition* was statistically
 505 significant [$F_{2, 17} = 4.49; p = .018; \eta^2 p = .199$]. Post-hoc comparisons revealed that
 506 participants committed more errors when the two principles competed in the similarity
 507 condition than when they competed in the proximity condition ($p = .055$). No other
 508 effects reached statistical significance.

509 3.2.2. Dominance dynamics and compatibility with additive effects

510 To further analyze the dominance dynamics obtained in this experiment and to
511 compare the results with those of Experiment 1, we first transformed the raw RTs by
512 computing a differential variable as follows: $I = \text{conjoined condition}$ (competitive or
513 cooperative) – single condition . Positive scores indicate the magnitude of the
514 interference (in ms) of the non-attended cue in the competitive condition, whereas
515 negative scores indicate the magnitude of the facilitation effect when the two grouping
516 cues act in cooperation. Table 3 summarizes the facilitation and interference scores. The
517 facilitation/interference scores were then normalized using effect sizes D ($D =$
518 $I/\text{Standard error of } I$). The D values were adjusted to fall between -1 and +1, by taking
519 the highest D value as 1 in the normalized scale and computing the rest of the
520 normalized effect sizes as the ratio between the observed D value and the highest D
521 value ($D / \text{highest } D \text{ value observed}$). The 0 value in the scale represents the scores for
522 the two single conditions. The normalized results are summarized in Fig. 5 and the
523 inferences about additivity are listed in Table 4,

524 **Fig. 5** Normalized effect sizes used to examine the additivity of the data from
525 Experiment 2. Cooperation between principles is identified by (○) and competition by
526 (÷). The grouping cue on the left is the attended one, and the grouping cue on the right
527 is the non-attended one. Positive scores indicate interference and negative scores
528 facilitation.

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535 **Table 4.** Inferences about the compatibility of the data from Experiment 2 with
 536 additivity effects of grouping.

Data	Inference	Relation to additivity		
		Compatible	Not incompatible	Incompatible
$D(s \circ p) > D(s)$	The O combination of s and p is stronger than s		✓	
$D(p \circ s) > D(p)$	The O combination of p and s is stronger than p		✓	
$D(s \div p) < D(s)$	The \div combination of p and s is not stronger than p	✓		
$D(p \div s) < D(p)$	The \div combination of p and s is not stronger than s	✓		
$D(p \circ s) > D(p \div s)$	The O combination of p and s is stronger than the \div combination of p and s	✓		
$D(s \circ p) > D(s \div p)$	The O combination of s and p is stronger than the \div combination of s and p	✓		
$D(p \circ s) > D(p) > D(p \div s)$	The O combination of p and s is stronger than p and the \div combination of p and s		✓	
$D(s \circ p) > D(s) > D(s \div p)$	The O combination of s and p is stronger than s and the \div combination of s and p		✓	

537 D represents the normalized measure of effect sizes; p , proximity; s , similarity; \circ ,
 538 cooperation; \div , competition. The first grouping cue within parentheses is the attended
 539 cue, whereas the second is the non-attended (interfering/facilitating) cue.

540 The results of the normalized effect sizes show that when the two principles
 541 competed, the interference effect of the proximity cue over texture similarity (i.e., when
 542 proximity was the non-attended cue in the similarity block) was greater than the
 543 interference effect of the similarity cue over proximity (when similarity was the non-
 544 attended cue). The same pattern of results appeared in the cooperative condition. The
 545 facilitation effect obtained was greater when proximity was the ignored cue, although
 546 the effect sizes in this condition were considerably smaller.

547 In sum, the results of Experiment 2 were compatible with the additive model of
548 grouping found in Experiment 1, and the tendency of proximity cues to dominate the
549 organization of the haptic scene when the two grouping principles were in competition.

550 **4. General discussion**

551 The current study examined the interactive effects between two main grouping
552 principles, spatial proximity and texture similarity in active touch. We investigated
553 whether a grouping principle dominated the perceptual organization of the haptic scene.
554 We also examined whether, as occurs in vision, the conjoined grouping effects in touch
555 were compatible with an additive model.

556 Experiment 1 showed grouping effects for both acting-alone grouping principles,
557 which did not differ in strength. The grouping effect for the cooperative condition was
558 stronger than the effect of each single principle alone. In addition, grouping effects
559 occurred even when the grouping principles were conjoined in competition, although
560 this effect was weaker than the effect of each principle alone. Interestingly, the positive
561 scores indicate a faint dominance of proximity, even when the two principles were
562 similar in perceived strength, as shown by the ratings in the acting-alone conditions (see
563 Fig. 3-left). Following the criteria introduced by Kubovy and van den Berg (2008), our
564 data are fully compatible with an additive model of grouping effects. Moreover, the
565 consistency analyses showed strong correlations between the strength of the conjoined
566 grouping conditions and the combination of single factor effects across participants.
567 Based on these results, we can conclude that the greater variability found in the
568 competitive condition was not a byproduct of the inconsistency of individual ratings,
569 but the consequence of the tendency of participants to group according to different
570 grouping cues when the perceptual organization was vague and/or unclear. Supporting
571 this conclusion, the analysis of the individual ratings in the competitive condition

572 indicated that 14 participants grouped by proximity and 5 by similarity, which also
573 explains the dominance of the proximity grouping when the two principles were
574 confronted.

575 The results of Experiment 1 in active touch are in agreement with those obtained in
576 vision by Quinlan & Wilton (1998) using a comparable task and similar grouping
577 principles (spatial proximity and color/shape similarity). In touch as in vision, the
578 perceived strength of grouping followed the same pattern, with the greatest grouping
579 strength in the cooperative condition, followed by acting alone and competitive
580 conditions. In addition, our results are compatible with an additive model of the
581 grouping effects in touch according to the criteria introduced by Kubovy and van den
582 Berg (2008). The main difference found in touch (Experiment 1) compared to findings
583 in the visual modality was the dominance of the proximity grouping cue when both
584 grouping principles compete. This result contrasts with the absence of dominance of
585 proximity over similarity found by Quinlan and Wilton (1998) in their visual study. A
586 possible explanation is that the single cues in their study were not matched in relative
587 salience as they were in our study. Interestingly, Luna and Montoro (2011) conducted a
588 visual experiment in which the relative salience of the grouping cues was previously
589 equated. They compared several intrinsic cues with the extrinsic grouping principle of
590 common region (Palmer, 1992). Their results showed that, when proximity and
591 common region were pitted against each other, common region dominated the
592 perceptual organization. This suggests that, although the laws that govern the interaction
593 between these grouping principles in vision and touch share common ground, the
594 specific grouping principles that dominate the haptic and visual scene may differ, which
595 is consistent with the fact that the most salient features in vision and touch differ
596 (Klatzky et al., 1987).

597 Experiment 2 yielded similar conclusions. The dominance of grouping by
600 proximity was explicit given 1) the significantly shorter RTs for groups formed by
601 proximity, and 2) the higher error rate for groups formed by texture similarity in the
602 competitive condition (proximity ignored), relative to groups formed by proximity
603 (texture similarity ignored) in the same condition. Interestingly, single cues were
604 responded to faster than competing cues, suggesting interference of the non-attended
605 cue in both similarity and proximity blocks of trials. Thus, even when the instructions
606 were to attend selectively to a specific grouping cue in each block and ignore the other,
607 responses were slowed by the presence of a competing irrelevant cue in the haptic field,
608 indicating that the non-attended cue was not completely inhibited and hindered motor
609 responses (Luna et al., 2016). This interference effect disagrees with the dominance of
610 proximity, given that it was bidirectional and symmetrical (same magnitude in both
611 directions), as can be inferred from the absence of a significant interaction between the
612 grouping condition and the attended cue. Despite this apparent contradiction, a further
613 analysis of the normalized effect sizes showed that the effect size of the interference
614 effect when proximity was the non-attended cue approximately doubled the effect size
615 of the interference when texture similarity was the non-attended cue, a result that
616 matches the difference between interferences scores. Thus, the normalization of the
617 effect sizes reveals that the interference effect is better described as bidirectional but
618 asymmetrical, fitting the previous evidence concerning the dominance of spatial
619 proximity in the perceptual organization of the haptic scene.

618 Experiment 2 also found a lack of facilitation effects of grouping principles acting
619 cooperatively relative to grouping cues acting alone, which contrasts with the strong
620 cooperative grouping effects found in the ratings of Experiment 1. These differences
621 could be explained by the different nature of the grouping measures (direct vs indirect)

622 and the different attentional demands of phenomenological and psychophysical tasks. In
623 the phenomenological task used in Experiment 1, the participants were asked to rate the
624 degree of grouping a central target with the elements on the right or left. No other
625 instructions were provided, attention was deployed over the whole stimuli, and there
626 was no time pressure. In the psychophysical task (Experiment 2), the participants had to
627 explicitly attend to a specific grouping cue in each block of trials while performing the
628 task as fast and accurately as possible. These differences in attentional requirements and
629 time constraints could underlie the differences observed, reflecting different sensitivities
630 in each task. In fact, this absence of facilitation in the cooperative condition has also
631 been found in other tasks in which interference/facilitation effects are tested. Notably,
632 MacLeod (1991) in his comprehensive review of the Stroop-like task literature (which
633 shares the same characteristics as the psychophysical task employed in Experiment 2)
634 said that even when facilitation exists, “this facilitation is much less than the
635 corresponding interference in the incongruent condition” (MacLeod, 1991, p.174). The
636 author argued that the most plausible reason for this result is the difficulty of speeding
637 up a response that is already fast, which could account for the absence of reliable
638 facilitation effects in our haptic study.

639 Finally, the normalization of the effect sizes (Experiment 2) allowed us to compare
640 the compatibility of the data with an additive model of interactive grouping effects. As
641 in Experiment 1, the results are compatible with an additive model based on the criteria
642 mentioned above (Kubovy & van den Berg, 2008). Specifically, the acting-alone
643 conditions fall between the two conjoined conditions. In addition, the order of the effect
644 sizes was consistent with the postulated dominance of the proximity cue, with larger
645 effect sizes in conjoined conditions when proximity is the non-attended irrelevant cue.

646 Taken together, several conclusions can be drawn from the results of the present
647 study. First, the participants could spontaneously group the tactile patterns without any
648 previous instructions in almost the same way as incidental/ phenomenological grouping
649 in the visual modality. This supports the idea that the internal perceptual grouping
650 processes operate similarly in vision and touch. Second, the interaction pattern is fairly
651 similar in the two modalities. This reinforces the conclusion that perceptual grouping
652 follows the same rules in vision and touch. Third, spatial proximity seems to dominate
653 the perceived organization of the haptic scene when grouping cues are confronted, even
654 when the two principles have similar perceived strengths; making a clear difference
655 with the results obtained in the visual modality (Luna & Montoro, 2011; Luna et al.,
656 2016). Finally, the results support the compatibility of the interaction between proximity
657 and similarity grouping principles in touch with an additive model.

658 **5. Limitations and Future directions**

659 The procedure presented here could be an important tool for the investigation of
660 perceptual organization in touch. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first attempt to
661 adapt methods used widely in the visual modality, and to extend the systematic and
662 quantitative study of the interactions between these two grouping principles to a
663 previously neglected sensory modality. Future research should expand both implicit and
664 explicit grouping cues under study and their combinations in order to obtain a
665 representative amount of data. This will allow generalization of the present findings to
666 draw a complete picture of the commonalities and differences between these two
667 sensory modalities. Previous research in vision suggests that different grouping
668 principles have different temporal courses and attentional demands (Ben-Av & Sagi,
669 1995; Kimchi & Razpurker-Apfeld, 2004). Thus, dissimilar patterns of interaction
670 between different grouping principles in touch deserve further investigation. Future

671 work should consider perceptual factors other than the classic grouping cues, such as
672 perceptual completion (Nir & Ben Shahar, 2015), symmetry (Ballesteros, Millar, &
673 Reales, 1998; Ballesteros & Reales, 2004), and statistical regularities (Dakin, 2015), in
674 order to study the complex interactions between different factors involved in the
675 organization of the haptic scene. Finally, a potential objective for future research is the
676 development of new tasks to overcome the potential limitations of the paradigms used
677 here. An interesting approach could be based on a combination of psychophysical tasks
678 and indirect (or implicit) measures of grouping (Palmer & Beck, 2007). This kind of
679 procedure combines the presence of an objective correct response with incidental
680 grouping to avoid the use of alternative strategies, unrelated to perceptual grouping
681 itself. In any case, beyond the (dis)advantages of each particular task, the use of a
682 convergent approach based on multiple methods should be a fruitful strategy for the
683 future study of perceptual grouping in touch.

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